

IMPACT OF IOT DEVICES ON NETWORKING TECHNOLOGIES AND SECURITY ISSUES

Khusenov Murodjon Zokhirovich

Lecturer at the Department of Information Systems and Digital Technologies at Bukhara State University

Article information:

Manuscript received: 21 Aug 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Sep 2024; **Published:** 23 Oct 2024

Abstract: The Internet of Things (IoT) has become an integral part of modern technology, transforming the way we live and work every day. IoT devices cover a wide range of technologies, from smart refrigerators to industrial monitoring systems. It is estimated that by 2030, the number of connected devices will reach 50 billion. Such growth will certainly have a significant impact on networks and pose new challenges, especially in the area of security.

Keywords: Internet of Things (IoT), modern technologies, IoT devices, connected devices, network technologies, increasing traffic volume, 5G, Low Power Wide Area Networks (LPWAN), decentralized architecture, blockchain, security, device vulnerability, lack of updates, unauthorized access, data privacy, security enhancement strategies.

How IoT Impacts Networking

With the advent of IoT, the number of devices interacting with each other via networks has increased significantly. These devices require reliable and fast connections, which creates a demand for more advanced and stable network technologies.

Increase in traffic volume

The first noticeable consequence of the growth of IoT is the increase in network traffic. Devices exchange data constantly, which puts existing network structures at risk. Large amounts of data require efficient management to prevent congestion and ensure high transmission speeds.

Every connected device generates information. Smart homes with multiple cameras, sensors, and controllers can generate terabytes of data daily. This requires high-bandwidth, low-latency networking technologies to support normal operational processes.

Application of new generation network technologies

As the popularity of IoT grows, new networking technologies such as 5G and Low Power Wide Area Networks (LPWAN) are being developed and deployed. 5G offers high data speeds and low latency, making it ideal for real-time applications such as autonomous vehicles or remote medical procedures.

LPWAN, on the other hand, is ideal for energy-dependent devices that require long battery life. This is important for aggregating data from sensors that may be far from power sources. Using network data, these devices can operate efficiently without generating a large amount of traffic.

Decentralized architecture

With the increasing number of devices, the use of decentralized network architectures becomes

relevant. Blockchain, as one example, ensures secure interaction between devices, maintaining confidentiality and data integrity. This allows not only to protect the network, but also to simplify the information exchange processes, eliminating the need for a central server.

Security Issues in the IoT Ecosystem

According to research, security issues remain one of the top risks for the IoT. Vulnerabilities in devices and networks can lead to serious consequences for both users and businesses.

Device vulnerability

Many IoT devices have limited resources, and manufacturers often focus their efforts on usability, forgetting about security. Defects and weaknesses in device software can provide opportunities for hackers to gain unauthorized access. An example is a number of vulnerabilities in smart cameras that allowed attackers to gain access to the video stream.

Lack of security updates is also a major issue. Many devices do not support automatic updates, leaving users at risk. Once a vulnerability is discovered, manufacturers must respond quickly and provide fixes, which is not always the case.

Threat of unauthorized access

Unauthorized access to an IoT network can lead to data compromise and even physical damage. Hacked devices can be used to access more important systems, creating a security threat to the entire infrastructure. This chain reaction can affect not only individual users but also large corporations.

You can protect your network with multi-factor authentication, data encryption, and updated security protocols. However, users often don't understand the importance of a strong password, and this lack of awareness leaves them vulnerable to attacks.

Data privacy issues

Another major issue is the collection and use of data generated by IoT devices. Devices collect huge amounts of personal information, including user location and behavior. If this information is leaked or accessed unauthorized, the consequences can be serious.

Companies' reputations can suffer if they do not protect their customers' data well. Data protection laws, such as the GDPR in Europe, place high demands on how companies handle and protect their customers' personal data. Failure to comply with such regulations can result in significant fines and losses.

Strategies to Improve IoT Security

Improving the security of the rest of the devices in the IoT ecosystem requires a comprehensive approach. From user education to the implementation of sophisticated technologies, all help minimize risks.

User education

Educating end users about potential security threats and necessary protection measures is of utmost importance. Seminars, training courses and information campaigns will help raise awareness of the importance of strong access control and timely software updates.

Users should understand how to create complex passwords and use unique identifiers for each device to minimize the risk of unauthorized access. Regularly updating software and firmware is also a critical step in ensuring security.

Integration of solutions with a high level of security

Companies can implement high-security solutions at the network architecture level. Using

encryption technologies, including SSL and IPsec, ensures the protection of transmitted data. Installing firewalls within the IoT network will also help limit unauthorized access.

Critical systems that rely on IoT should have clearly defined incident response protocols. This approach allows for the rapid identification and elimination of threats, minimizing the consequences. It is also worth considering the use of automation, which will allow for a prompt response to suspicious behavior on the network.

Collaboration with security partners

Companies should be open to collaboration with security experts and vendors. Joint efforts and sharing of cyber threat intelligence will help identify vulnerabilities and implement new defense methods.

Large companies can form alliances with cybersecurity startups to leverage their innovative approaches and technologies to improve overall security. This collaboration also has implications for joint threat analysis and risk assessment.

The Role of the State in Regulating IoT Security

Clear regulatory frameworks and legislation are needed to ensure IoT security. Countries can pass laws that require devices to be manufactured with security in mind from the start. This could close many known vulnerabilities at the design stage.

Safety standards

Security standards for IoT devices should be clearly defined and enforced internationally. Creating global norms will avoid fragmented regulations and long-running debates about liability in the event of data breaches.

Also, monitoring and control over compliance with these standards will provide a higher level of protection than is currently the case. In addition, research into successful practices and studying international experience will help harmonize approaches to regulation.

Research activities

Public and private organizations can invest in research projects that explore new approaches to secure IoT network operation. In-field research and development of new threat identification methods will help improve the current state of security systems. Such initiatives can not only improve the security situation, but also help increase user confidence in IoT technologies.

Public and private organizations can focus on several key areas when investing in IoT security research and development projects.

First, this is the development of new cryptographic algorithms that are resistant to quantum computing. Existing encryption algorithms can be cracked by sufficiently powerful quantum computers, which makes the search for post-quantum cryptography and its integration into IoT devices critically important. This requires not only mathematical research, but also the development of efficient hardware and software solutions that take into account the limited computing power of many IoT devices. Projects should focus on developing lightweight, energy-efficient algorithms that provide a high degree of protection with minimal resource consumption.

The second promising area is the development of methods for detecting and preventing attacks based on traffic and device behavior analysis. Here, it is necessary to develop machine learning systems capable of identifying anomalies in the operation of IoT networks, such as unexpectedly high data volumes, unusual requests, or atypical device behavior. These systems must be intelligent enough to distinguish real threats from false positives, minimizing the number of false positives that can lead to false alarms and system shutdowns. It is also necessary

to develop self-learning mechanisms to adapt to new types of attacks and threat evolution. Research in this area should take into account the specifics of different types of IoT devices and networks, since each of them has its own unique structure and vulnerabilities.

The third line of research should focus on developing secure authentication and authorization mechanisms. This includes developing new authentication protocols that use biometrics or other sophisticated methods to protect against credential forgery and theft. It is also important to ensure secure key and certificate management, preventing unauthorized access to them.

Particular attention should be paid to developing mechanisms that ensure security throughout the entire life cycle of a device, from the manufacturing stage to disposal. This includes protection against hardware counterfeiting and ensuring secure firmware updates. In addition, research should be conducted in the field of physical security of IoT devices. This includes developing methods for protecting against physical access and hacking, such as the use of protected housings, tamper-proof components, and tamper detection methods. Developing security standards for different types of IoT devices is also an important task.

These standards must be clear, understandable and easy to implement by manufacturers, ensuring a high degree of compatibility and interoperability between different devices and systems. All this research must be accompanied by the development of new threat identification methods, including software and hardware vulnerability analysis. This requires the creation of specialized tools and platforms for automated security analysis, which will significantly speed up the process of detecting and eliminating vulnerabilities.

Research results should be made available to a wide range of IoT device developers and manufacturers to help improve the security of the entire ecosystem. Only a comprehensive approach that includes both fundamental research and practical development of new technologies will significantly improve IoT security and ensure user confidence in these technologies.

Conclusion

The impact of IoT on network technologies cannot be underestimated. The increase in the number of connected devices creates both opportunities and challenges. The main challenge in this context is ensuring the security of data and systems, which requires increased attention from users, manufacturers and regulators.

User education, the use of modern security technologies, and collaboration between the public and private sectors are key to successful risk management. It is important that all participants in the IoT ecosystem work together to create a safe and secure environment that fosters innovation and prosperity.

Returning to these principles will be critical to the future of the Internet of Things and its integration into society.

List of references

1. Kozhevnikova I.S. Internet of Things Security Trends // Young Scientist. 2017. No. 13 (147). P. 11-14.
2. Maslova M.A. Principles of Internet of Things Security // Bulletin of the Ural Federal District. Security in the Information Sphere. 2018. No. 3 (29). P. 38-42.
3. M.Z. Khusenov, F.Kh.Khazratov Expert system: concept, definition and classification of expert systems Journal of scientific information of Bukhara state universities, 2020, issue 1, 03/25/2020. pp. 88-92

4. O. Umurov , M. Z Khusenov , Sh . Boltaev Security informational security V higher educational institution "Pedagogical akmeology" international scientific-methodical journal 1(1)2022 pp :152-154